

Welcome resources and information for incoming IPBES assessment experts

Introduction

The goal of this document is to provide a list of resource links for the incoming assessment experts, as well as a brief overview of the assessment process, of the roles and responsibilities of authors, and of the role of the IPBES task forces regarding IPBES assessments.

1. Important resource links

- a. Guide to the production of assessments and information on completed and ongoing assessments
 - i. [The IPBES guide on the production of assessments](#)
 - ii. Previous and ongoing assessments (see materials associated with completed assessments—e.g., [Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services](#) and [Assessment Report on Land Degradation and Restoration](#))
 - iii. [Nexus assessment - mandate and scoping report](#)
 - iv. [Transformative change assessment - mandate and scoping report](#)
 - v. [Roles and responsibilities of assessment experts](#)
- b. E-learning, online resources and webinars
 - i. [E-learning modules](#) (e.g., on the IPBES conceptual framework, assessment process and data management policy)
 - ii. [IPBES webinar series](#) (e.g., on previous assessments, the IPBES conceptual framework and the assessment process)
 - iii. [IPBES information communication \(ICT\) documentation](#) (e.g., data management tutorials, technical guidance on the development of maps, and guidance on the use of the data management tool Zenodo)
 - iv. [IPBES data management policy](#)
 - v. [IPBES conceptual framework](#)
 - vi. [IPBES glossary](#)
- c. [Procedures for the preparation of IPBES deliverables](#)
- d. [IPBES structure](#)
- e. [IPBES conflict of interest policy](#)
- f. [IPBES code of conduct for experts](#)

2. IPBES assessments

IPBES assessments synthesize and critically evaluate peer-reviewed scientific literature, grey literature and other knowledge. Assessments do not involve the undertaking of new primary research, but assessments do entail re-analysis of data and models to address specific questions. One major aspect of IPBES assessments is that they are meant to be policy-relevant, but not policy prescriptive. Assessments need to be credible, legitimate and relevant and should reference the IPBES conceptual framework and express the reliability of evidence using confidence language. Assessments are subject to public review and to approval by governments. *See the IPBES guide on the production of assessments (link above) for detailed information on assessments.*

**Figure taken from the IPBES guide on the production of assessments illustrating the steps from requests for assessment topics to scoping to approval of the assessment and summary for policymakers at Plenary. Also see the [e-learning module on the assessment process](#).*

There are different types of IPBES assessments:

- a. *Global assessments* assess biodiversity and ecosystem services and their interlinkages at the global scale.
- b. *Regional assessments* assess biodiversity and ecosystem services and their interlinkages at the regional and, as necessary, sub-regional levels (completed regional assessments include those for Africa, the Americas, Asia and the Pacific, and Europe and Central Asia).
- c. *Thematic assessments* assess a particular theme at an appropriate scale (ongoing/completed thematic assessments include those of pollinators, pollination and food production; land degradation and restoration; invasive alien species and their control; and sustainable use of wild species).
- d. *Methodological assessments* assess the availability and use of methods in relation with a specific topic (ongoing/completed methodological assessments include those on values and scenarios and models) so that these methods can then be used in IPBES assessments and other activities.

3. Assessment expert roles and guidance on fulfilling these roles

- a. *Management committees*: Consist of the co-chairs, appointed members of the IPBES Multidisciplinary Expert Panel and Bureau, as well as representatives from the dedicated technical support unit (*see detailed information on the role of technical support units on page 19 of the guide to the production of assessments*) and secretariat.

They are responsible for supporting the co-chairs of the relevant assessment in the day-to-day operations required for the implementation of the respective deliverable, where the substance of the matter to be addressed does not warrant alerting the full Multidisciplinary Expert Panel, Bureau or other entity responsible according to the IPBES procedures.

General guidance for the management committees:

- i. Support the co-chairs and assist the Bureau and Multidisciplinary Expert Panel in overseeing assessment processes, and assist with issues such as filling gaps in expertise.
 - ii. Stay up to date with all developments of the assessment and ensure that the processes adhere to all relevant IPBES procedures. Where the management committee cannot agree on an issue, or the scope of the matter to be addressed warrants a decision by the responsible body, the matter will be referred by the management committee to the responsible body.
 - iii. Ensure the approaches and findings of the assessment are consistent.
 - iv. Oversee the preparation of the summary for policymakers and its presentation to the Plenary.
 - v. Hold regular teleconferences.
- b. *Co-chairs*: Assume responsibility for overseeing the preparation of an assessment report, including its summary for policymakers, ensuring that the report is completed to the highest scientific standard and responds to the scoping report.

General guidance for fulfilling the role of co-chair:

- i. Review applicable IPBES procedures, as well as other assessments and relevant deliverables.

- ii. Organize regular online meetings with chapter coordinating lead authors to follow the development of the chapters.
 - iii. Invest in building trust and community amongst the authors as well as a sense of pride and ownership of the assessment process.
 - iv. Review and check the key messages of the chapters in order to prepare the summary for policymakers.
- c. *Coordinating lead authors*: Assume overall responsibility for coordinating major sections and/or chapters of the assessment report. Coordinating lead authors are lead authors who have the added responsibility of coordinating the work of the lead authors, fellows and contributing authors involved in their chapter to ensure the highest scientific quality of the chapter as a whole.

General guidance for fulfilling the role of coordinating lead author:

- i. Allocate tasks amongst lead authors and identify the areas that each lead author will be assigned.
 - ii. Organize regular communication between the lead authors and fellows in the chapter.
 - iii. Review the text on a regular basis and structure the text and figures, tables and text boxes to create a flowing chapter.
 - iv. Set deadlines for the author team to deliver text in time for the delivery of the different drafts and review processes.
 - v. Identify gaps in the chapter author team and identify potential contributing authors to fill those gaps.
 - vi. Ensure that any cross-cutting issues of significance to more than one section in the chapter are addressed in a complete and coherent manner.
- d. *Lead authors*: Assume responsibility for the production of designated sections or parts of chapters in line with the scoping report for the assessment, on the basis of the best scientific and technical information available. The essence of the lead authors' role is to synthesize material drawn from the available literature and fully justified unpublished sources.

General guidance for fulfilling the role of lead author:

- i. Actively participate in discussions within the chapter team about the content of the chapter.
 - ii. Get familiar with previous IPBES assessments to learn about the style and overall standards expected.
 - iii. Identify existing evidence (data, scientific and grey literature, indigenous and local knowledge) as a basis for drafting dedicated chapter's section. When gaps are identified in the chapter, consider where a contributing author could be called upon to fill them.
- e. *Review editors*: Ensure that all substantive expert and government review comments are afforded appropriate consideration, advise lead authors on how to handle contentious or controversial issues, and ensure that genuine controversies are adequately reflected in the text of the report concerned.

General guidance for fulfilling the role of review editor:

- i. Get accustomed to the content of the chapter.
- ii. Consider who would be suitable candidates for performing the expert review.

- iii. Refrain from imposing changes in the text to the author team.
 - iv. Review the responses by authors to comments received.
 - v. Be a good partner to the author team and make good judgement calls.
- f. *Fellows*: Develop sections or parts of chapters in collaboration with coordinating lead authors and lead authors.

General guidance for fulfilling the role of fellows:

- i. Coordinate role in the chapter with the chapter's coordinating lead authors and lead authors.
- ii. Actively participate in discussions within the chapter team about the content of the chapter.
- iii. Get familiar with previous IPBES assessments to learn about the style and overall standards expected.
- iv. Identify existing evidence (data, scientific and grey literature, indigenous and local knowledge) as a basis for drafting dedicated chapter's section. When gaps are identified in the chapter, consider where a contributing author could be called upon to fill them.
- v. Seek advice and guidance from mentor(s) and other relevant authors.

4. IPBES task forces

The five IPBES task forces - on capacity building, policy support, knowledge and data, indigenous and local knowledge, and scenarios and models - develop guidance on specific topics related to their area of work. Each task force has a unique mandate and objective(s). The technical support unit of the assessment acts as the main point of contact between assessment experts and the task forces.

- a. The [capacity-building task force](#) builds capacities of individuals and institutions for a strengthened science-policy interface for biodiversity and ecosystem services through enhanced learning and engagement, facilitated access to expertise and information, and strengthened national and regional capacities.

Key activities related to the development of IPBES assessments include the following: coordination of the [IPBES fellowship programme](#) and the training and familiarization programme; development of [e-learning resources](#) and [webinars](#) on IPBES deliverables and processes; development of on-demand writing and training workshops for IPBES experts to further develop their capacities to contribute to IPBES assessments; organize dialogue meetings bringing together IPBES national focal points and other Government representatives and stakeholders to engage in dialogues with IPBES experts during the review periods of assessment drafts; work with IPBES experts to support the uptake of assessments; and encouragement of the development of communities of practice around IPBES assessments and other deliverables.

- b. The [policy support tools and methodologies task force](#) supports the use of policy instruments, policy support tools and methodologies in the implementation of the work programme in the assessments, as well as the uptake of the findings of the assessments in decision-making; and catalyses the further development of policy instruments, support tools and good practices to fill gaps identified in IPBES assessments.

Key activities related to the development of IPBES assessments include the following: development of [guidance on how to assess policy instruments and facilitate the use of policy](#)

[support tools and methodologies through IPBES assessments](#); provision of on-demand support to authors of the chapters dealing with policy options/responses in the application of the guidance; and peer-review of draft scoping documents, draft chapters and summaries for policymakers of ongoing assessments to increase their policy relevance.

- c. The [indigenous and local knowledge \(ILK\) task force](#) develops methods and works with assessment authors to implement the IPBES [approach to recognizing and working with ILK](#), which includes a series of activities that have the dual aim of including ILK in assessments and facilitating the [participation of indigenous peoples and local communities \(IPLCs\) in the assessment processes](#). IPBES recognizes that IPLCs possess detailed knowledge relating to understanding, managing and sustainably using biodiversity, and is committed to working with ILK and IPLCs in its assessments.

Key activities related to the development of the assessment include the following: provision of [methodological guidance](#) for recognizing and working with ILK; organization of dialogue workshops on ILK at key points in the assessment process; provision of support for the ILK liaison group of each assessment (a group of authors tasked with working with ILK); provision of support to the development of key framing questions on ILK for the assessment; coordination of a call for contributions for each assessment, which gives an opportunity for IPLCs to provide information or case studies and to recommend networks, organizations or individuals who could be engaged in the assessment process; provision of support to literature reviews and sourcing and review of diverse materials of relevance to the assessment; peer-review of assessment drafts; organization of side-events and other communication and information-sharing activities at relevant international meetings during an assessment; outreach and follow up with IPLCs after an assessment is completed; and provision of support to the implementation of free, prior and informed consent throughout the assessment process.

- d. The [knowledge and data task force](#) recognizes the importance of raising awareness on IPBES-identified knowledge gaps and of accessing and managing data for the implementation of the IPBES work programme. To implement work on knowledge and data, activities have been grouped under two main components: *data management* and *new knowledge generation*. The data management component develops, reviews, and supports the implementation of the IPBES data management policy throughout IPBES; supports the generation, handling, and delivery of IPBES products; and engages with external initiatives and providers on data. On knowledge generation, the task force supports the process of knowledge gaps identification by IPBES assessments experts; promotes awareness and use of identified gaps by engaging research programming organizations; and monitors and follows up on how new knowledge generated helps fill identified gaps.

Key activities related to the development of IPBES assessments include the following: provision of support to assessment experts specifically regarding the implementation of the [IPBES data management policy](#), provision of [guidance](#) on the development of data management reports, applications of natural language processing, and [handling of spatial data](#), including remote sensing enabled essential variables and indicators; development and updating of a process to catalyze the generation of new knowledge, living guidelines and templates to support authors in the process of [identifying knowledge gaps](#); organization of dialogue workshops with IPBES experts and relevant external organizations to promote the uptake of identified knowledge needs; and monitoring of the impact of [knowledge generation catalysis efforts](#) to effectively fill identified gaps.

- e. The [scenarios and models task force](#) builds on the [IPBES Scenarios and Models Assessment](#) and continues work on scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services. It works to catalyze the development of nature-centred multi-scale scenarios for a sustainable future and to facilitate cross-scale and cross-sectoral coordination to assess and reverse declines in biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Key activities related to the development of IPBES assessments include the following: Provision of support to assessments and of expert advice to assessment authors on the use of [currently available scenarios and models](#) to address current IPBES needs; peer-review of assessment drafts, specifically focusing on scenarios and models; provision of support, as requested by assessment authors, with additional resources or information on scenarios and models; publication of articles in peer-reviewed journals to stimulate the development of scenarios and models tailored to IPBES assessments; catalyzation of the further development of scenarios and models (e.g., using the [Nature's Futures Framework](#)) by the broader scientific community for future IPBES assessments; and provision of methodological guidance on the use of the Nature Futures Framework for catalyzing the development of the next generation of scenarios for biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services.